

Anti Corruption

Strategies and Interventions

By Artur Victoria

- Relationship between citizen and state institutions 'equilibrium social contract'
 - How are institutions linked politically and functionally both internally and to civil society
 - Which institutions are needed and how should they perform?

A recent definition of state building, which is a similar concept, is the political and institutional structures that negotiate the mutual demands between state and citizen.

Let us start with looking at where we are trying to get. The purpose of Anti Corruption is part of a package of interventions aimed at improving the well being of its citizens in the long term.

Some consensus on what sort of picture this presents has been arrived at in western countries. The picture is commonly displayed as a temple. Others have used the metaphor of the Birds Nest.

We come back about the implications of these metaphors later; however, they are an attempt to characterise a core or less complex set of structures that sustain this relationship between citizens and the state.

Greed and Opportunity

Corruption = Monopoly plus Discretion minus Accountability

This rule of thumb has proved useful in identifying potential weaknesses in systems and was very influential in first generation Anti Corruption reforms.

Early Interventions

- Create legal framework
- Reduce number of transactions vulnerable to corruption
- Reduce gains from corrupt transactions
- Increase probability of being caught

- Increase magnitude of penalties

These interventions tended to be rather macro. The enabling system was the focus. Laws and institutional forms were put in place. Economic models were very influential – an incentives based approach was largely adopted.

The reduction of corruption was considered as an end in itself – quite often became divorced from its broader developmental goals.

- First point
- Early interventions really driven by development economics. The problem is the greed and discretionary power of government officials. Largely done without empirical evidence.
- Second point
- Led to assumptions that if you do this across the board, governance indicators will improve, and so development outcomes. The problem is that this led to the prevalence of a number of different bodies with responsibility for the fight against corruption.

Critique of Greed and Discretion

- Can undermine necessary state interventions
- Does not always support immediate political stability needs
- Establishing stable efficient property rights for markets takes time and resources
- Anti Corruption interventions should not reduce the cohesiveness and effectiveness of the state

Note the wide variety of stability of property rights that exist even in China, but commonly in many developing and transition countries. Therefore, recognising the real stability of the President should be a basis for the appropriateness of Anti Corruption measures. Capacity and regulation should go hand in hand.

Interventions that permit corruption risk institutionalising the practice.

Example of Importance of the historical and political context:

In former Yugoslav states, during the wars, a close relationship developed between smuggling and organized crime and political elites; confronting organized crime now also means implicating people in power and there is considerable resistance to that;

In Bosnia & Herzegovina, primary objective of international community has been to maintain peace and allow some level of functioning of the state; corruption of many elected politicians has been tolerated in order to achieve these higher objectives;

In Kosovo, Montenegro, and Serbia, preoccupation with statehood has lowered the priority of governance questions; these could be de facto ignored due to much more “important” questions of independence, and subsequent state-building processes (last hurdle in Montenegro the adoption of a Constitution);

In Montenegro, the question of size: very small country, small elite, inherently non-competitive; nepotism a greater problem than elsewhere, where many conflict of interest provisions cannot be effectively applied due to statistical probability that elites are related;

In Bosnia & Herzegovina, the Dayton institutional structure extremely complex, with the layers of competencies between state -, entity -, and cantonal-level authorities creating additional hurdles for reform

Of course, there is throughout the Western Balkans the shared legacy of the inefficient socialist bureaucracy, lack of a market economy, lack of competitiveness

Johnston's Syndromes

Recall the causes of corruption – this approach infers institutional challenges from socio-economic conditions.

Aims at simplifying some of the contextual characteristics and indicating peer countries for learning.

Hard sometimes to feel comfortable with where the country ends up.

Where would you place Bangladesh? It is in fact classed in the Clan quadrant.

This may help to understand the types of corruption that exist and sorts of phenomena that are likely to be associated with this style of authority. It may also help to think through how this sort of network may respond to immediate conditions or to a specific group or phenomenon.

Illustrations may be not accurate, just a simply indicative.

Examples:

Oligarchy/Clan - Russia, Afghanistan Philippines

Elite Cartels - Korea, Transition countries

Influence Market - US, UK etc.

Official Mogul - Command bureaucracy (China etc.)

Characteristics of syndromes

Influence Market:

Money politics - relatively strong institutions - 'idea of renting access'

Elite cartel

Hegemony of a group - relatively weak institutions. Participation recent

Oligarch/Clan

Risky/violent. Often much faster growth in wealth than institutional controls.

Official Mogul

Official plunder. Official immunity Participation the lowest.

100 countries mapped into these quadrants.

Can you place the authority network for your country?

Anti Corruption measures recommended by the World Bank

- Raising awareness with public in seminars
- Raising awareness with public administrators in seminars
- Establishing an ethics office
- Establishing an anti corruption agency
- Raising public sector wages
- Reducing wage compression
- Frying a big fish
- Appointing an enlightened leader

Evidence that it leads to action

- Raising Awareness NO
- Transparency and Accountability YES
- Civil Society development YES
- Participation in workshops NO
- Service Delivery surveys NO

Although the Khan analysis is not shared by all, it is in part reflected in a shift towards less macro incentives to more managerial and informational (Transparency and Accessibility)

From Anwar Shah Refines the areas of opportunity for strategies based on both corruption levels and governance capacities

In other words we need to look at both the problem and the ability of the institutions to absorb and implement the interventions.

- *High Corruption Low Governance*
 - Establish rule of law, strengthen institutions of participation and accountability; limit government interventions to focus on core mandate
- *Medium Corruption Medium Governance*

- Decentralization and economic policy reforms results-oriented, management and evaluation; introduction of incentives for competitive public service delivery
- *Low Corruption Good Governance*
 - Explicit anti-corruption programs such as anti-corruption agencies; strengthen financial management; raising public and officials awareness; no bribery pledges, fry big fish, etc.

• Methods	Effectiveness	
	Higher income	Lower income
• More commitment by politicians	1	4
• Internal control and supervision	2	1
• Transparent party finances	3	2
• Example given by mgmt at the top	4	8
• Influencing attitude of public servants	5	11
• Combating organised crime	6	6
• More public exposure	7	8
• Creating independent institutions	8	5
• Stronger selection of public personnel	9	3
• Reasonable standard of living	10	7
• (n)	(190)	(67)

Huberts 1998

Strengths of This Approach

- Better understanding of causes and consequences
- Recognition of individual and institutional ability to contribute
- Importance of collaborations and partnerships
- Better diagnostic tools

- Civil Society role vital
- Diversity of the problem
- Indirect measures are often best for AC
- Local and sectoral interventions needed

From the DAC report on AC experience

Just to review again: many of the most common failures of AC interventions seem to be related to those we associate with Anti Corruption strategy.

Weaknesses of Current Approaches

- **Tendency to rely on external experts**
- Low level of long term partnership
- **Too few actors involved in interventions**
- History of Policy Failure
- **Lack of context sensitivity**
- Over funding and pressure to disburse
- **Focus on infrastructure**
- Poor supervision of projects
- Reluctance to intervene in domestic affairs
- **Defensiveness and lack of transparency**
- Pressure to recover loans

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Contemporary – Sectoral & Themed

- Industry-specific transparency initiatives
- Independent monitoring of large procurement or concession awards
- Generation of credible information (diagnostics, surveys, etc.)

- Asset declaration regimes
- Support to economic diversification – strengthening small and medium-sized enterprises, promoting business associations, etc.
- Aid conditionality – ex. The Millennium Challenge Account

Success stories such as HK and Singapore had significant support and resources and in the case of Singapore it is seen as part of the national project.

Partial Successes reflected in changes in one or more governance indicators.

Botswana is said to have had low levels to start with, its triumph is to have maintained them.

- Comprehensive national successes, quite rare
 - Hong Kong, Singapore
 - Costa Rica, Botswana, Chile, Latvia, Estonia,
- Partial national successes

Venezuela, Uganda, Bulgaria, Georgia

- Sectoral successes
 - Education, Taxation, Customs
 - FOI

Source USAID AC handbook

If these are the most common reason for failure of Anti Corruption interventions, then they are not strategies at all but plans, as strategies would have accommodate these challenges. Here there is a lack of political will, inadequate power and resources, overambitious, uncoordinated, too dependent on law enforcement, targeting only middle ranking officials, failure to deliver quick wins, failure to institutionalise reforms.

What does contemporary strategy look like and what can we learn?

HOW TO PLAN A STRATEGY

The planning process at Kaiser Aluminium, circa 1964. Reprinted with permission of the Free Press, a Division of Simon & Schuster Adult Publishing Group, from *TOP MANAGEMENT PLANNING* by George A. Steiner. Copyright © 1969 by George A. Steiner. All rights reserved.

Early Strategic Plans

Dimensions of Strategy

Strategy is a **plan**

Strategy is a **ploy**

Strategy is a **pattern**

Strategy is a **position**

Strategy is a **perspective**

LIKE A GUIDELINE, CONSCIOUS, LIKE A NACS PLOY:

TO OUTWIT OPPONENTS, GIVEN THAT YOU HAVE A LOSER, THINKING OF A WAY TO UNDERMINE YOUR WORK, HOW WILL YOU GET ROUND HIM. THIS IS THE ARGUMENT ABOUT THE PORTER FORCES.

PATTERN:

EMERGENT, LIKE REFORMS THAT COME TO BE SEEN TO FIGHT C EFFECTIVELY. CUSTOMS.

POSITION

CLARIFY WHAT YOU STAND FOR. RELATE YOURSELF IN DISTINCTION TO OTHER ACTORS. WE ARE FOR BETTER SERVICE DELIVERY, THAT'S YOUR POSITION.

PERSPECTIVE

SINGAPORE, BOTSWANA, IT FITS IN A PARTICULAR NATIONAL WAY OF DOING THINGS. VISION. AC INTERVENTIONS ARE HARD WORK.

CAN BE SAPPING TO A TEAM, FROUGHT WITH DIFFICULTY. REQUIRE SOMETHING THAT GIVES THEM A MOTIVATING FORCE. THE MOTIVATIONAL ASPECT IS KEY.

COULD MAKE THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN SUCCESS AND FAILURE FOR A TECHNICALLY ADEQUATE INTERVENTION.

Contemporary Strategy

- Mixed data sources about needs and impact
- Planning
- Organisational awareness
 - Includes political and motivational issues
- Contextual and competitive sensitivity
- A mix of mutually supportive activities
- Leveraging Intangible Assets (e.g. knowledge, competence, leadership)
- Constant review/learning
- The CPIA provides indicators of the likely pressure towards corruption on institutions from the broader community
- More strategic, actionable focus
- More focus on transaction network and externalities
- More recognition of the importance of the context
- Less aggregation

- Use both qualitative and quantitative data
- More care in comparing
- More caution in claims and simplifications

The realm of corruption and integrity is one of institutions in social and economic contexts.

Using SWOT

SWOT focuses you on some of the characteristics of an institution and a setting that will be useful for competitive strategy.

- build on strengths
- minimize weaknesses
- seize opportunities
- counter threats

Indeed, you might see things in terms of answers to these four questions:

How can strengths be used to take advantage of opportunities?

How can strengths be used to avoid or defuse threats?

How can weaknesses be overcome to take advantage of opportunities?

How can weaknesses be overcome to counteract or minimize threats?

To correctly use this tool one should try to identify evidence for each, and if possible some measure of it. The danger otherwise is to formalise your assumptions. It is for this reason that measures and indicators are so central to Anti Corruption strategy. Unless evidence is produced, as we have seen, one can end up focusing on activities that are ineffective.

Another key point about SWOT is that you build on the strengths and cover the weaknesses.

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